

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Tewelde**FIRST NAME:** Asmerom**PROGRAM CODE :** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Kabiru GULMA

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 7)

WRITING SUCCESSFUL ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper explores the material in period one, which mainly deals with the basics of essay writing and important tips for writing a good essay.

Essay writing could be tedious and time-consuming task especially for people like myself which English is not our first language. The first part of the material focuses on steps for writing professional essay. Essay writing is not putting everything you know in paper. It requires understanding of the topic you want to write about.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is an important component of any discipline. As highlighted in the material, essay writing is not an easy task. It requires a lot of hard working and dedication to master it. Most importantly, understanding what constitutes a good essay and the basic steps for writing a good essay. The material in the coursepack describes in great detail the work required to write a good essay with tips that facilitate the writing process. Some of the steps are familiar from my undergraduate courses in English. It refreshes my memory and adds many new ideas that are paramount for writing. The aim of a professional essay is to convince readers to a specific argument. Therefore, it should have an essay question which is backed by evidence and the evidence should be analyzed by the author (EUCLID 2015, 2). The material clearly discusses how to read for your essay and how to take notes systematically as they are the basis for the essay.

When writing an essay, the author should consider some points. As mentioned in the above paragraph, an essay thesis is an important component of a good essay and should be mentioned at the beginning of the first paragraph. A good essay is usually

focused in the main points that the author is interested to discuss. There should not be generalization or conclusion as such thing could lead to unnecessary destruction to the readers (EUCLID 2015, 43). Another important thing that this material explore was the structure of the essay. It was highlighted that the essay should have 3 structures: namely Introduction, Body, and Conclusion. The material recommends that introduction and conclusion be written after the body once we become familiar with our topic (EUCLID 2015, 4)

A good essay should answer the thesis of the essay in a direct and systematic way. The argument provided in the essay should be supported with a balanced evidence that is evidence that support your argument as well as that are against your argument should be reflected (EUCLID 2015, 43). When writing a good essay, author should take into accounts, plagiarism, grammar, and writing style among others.

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is one form of academic crime. It is both unethical and unfair to take the work of others without giving them the necessary credit for their work (EUCLID 2015, 9). It occurs in two forms. Using the exact word of an author and fail to put it under quotations and to use work of other authors without citing even after paraphrase (EUCLID 2015, 43).

Citation is the scape boat for such office. When citing an academic work, one should consider two things. The fist is in text citation which has two forms quotations and paraphrasing. Quotations are the direct words of the author. If one wishes to take the direct quote from others, they should be put under quotation marks. Their use should be limited and only use when it is crucial to the argument we made (EUCLID 2015, 22). Paraphrase means to use someone else's idea in your own word. (EUCLID 2015, 23). Both paraphrase and quote should be cited as name of author, date, and page number (EUCLID 2015, 16). Before reading this material, I used to treat long quotations as short quotations and put them under quotation marks instead making them indented (EUCLID 2015, 20). In addition, the material also provides a very good information how to properly paraphrase (EUCLID 2015, 24).

4) WRITING STYLE

Style guide is a tool to make our writing consistent throughout the writing. Many organizations use their writing guide to allow more than one author to work on the same essay and still the writing style be consistent (EUCLID 2015, 52). Many freelancer writers do not govern by a particular writing guide but it is important for those writers to adapt to a prescribed writing style guide of the organization they are writing for (EUCLID 2015, 53). For the purpose of this course, it is recommended to use Chicago Rules (Turabian) but any other internationally recognized guide is acceptable. In this course or in any writing it is good practice to be consistent to the guideline of our choice.

Style guides go beyond punctuation and grammar which are well established elements of style. They encompass many elements such as preferred sentence length, layout, and format to name a few. While academic or technical writers take into consideration of writing style, creative writers do not follow these rules (EUCLID 2015, 24). Whether you write an academic essay or creative writing, you need to follow some rule in English. Crib Sheet the Chicago Style and Usage is discussed as an example of a style guide. It deals with many of the issues in style and enriched my understanding of Abbreviations, Initials/acronyms, and Geographical Terms to name a few.

a) Punctuation

One of the most important things in writing an academic essay is the use of proper punctuation marks. Similar to other elements of writing styles, punctuation should be consistent (EUCLID 2015, 7). The use of punctuation like commas, periods, and quotation marks differ from style to style and even more noticeably varies between Standard American English and Standard British English. To avoid such disparity in punctuation use, it is recommended to use either Standard American English and Standard British English and be consistent throughout your work.

b) Standard American or British English

Apply Although both types of English are similar in many ways and they are branches of World English, there are some variations in the pronunciation, spelling, and meaning. Though variations are attributed to cultural and historical differences (EUCLID 2015, 54). Despite these slight differences, both English are acceptable in essay writing but the writers should be consistent throughout and avoid mixing them up.

In this course the basic difference between Standard American English and Standard British English were discussed in depth. I have been using American English in my previous writing. Although I was not clear about their basic differences I thought that the only difference they have was just spelling and pronunciation. To make my writing consistent and avoid mixing up spelling, I was using Microsoft Word to guide me in my writing.

The course provided me with a plethora of information on how to correctly use commas, periods, quotation marks and how to write dates which cannot be found in office applications like Microsoft Word.

c) The use of Latin abbreviations and expressions

The material ends its discussion by providing a list of Latin aberrations and excretions along with their English meaning. Although, it is appropriate to use those expressions and abbreviations in an informal writing, it is not recommended to use them in academic essays since the purpose of academic writing is to persuade readers to the issues at hand (EUCLID 2015, 78). They are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing.

while formal writing it is recommended to use their English equivalent of the abbreviation (EUCLID 2015, 78). The use of abbreviations should be limited situation were their meaning is clear to reader (EUCLID 2015, 66). From long list of abbreviations and expressions in Latin provided in the course material, I gain not only how to use them in academic writing (example their usage inside parenthesis) and the meaning of many which encounter me in different essay.

5) **CONCLUSION**

Academic essay should be clear and simple that readers should understand them at first read. Finally, the material covered in period one seems common sense at first sight, they are filled with many information that are paramount for a writer. I have gained a lot of information which will be useful for my future writing.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://EUCLIDuniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.